

OSCAR Conceptual and Technical Framework for Researcher Well-being and Career Development Training and Mentoring

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Introduction

After successfully defending their PhDs, most new doctors and postdocs struggle to remain employed in jobs that match the level of their qualifications. Besides excelling in traditional “hard”, research-specific skills, early career researchers (ECR) therefore also need to acquire a number of “soft”, transferable skills to increase their employability not only inside, but also outside of the academic sector.

Early career researchers are expected to be creative, innovative, and resilient thinkers who can communicate their research to multicultural and diverse audiences. They also have to keep up with the latest demands in their field, such as those deriving from open science practices and digitization. Besides, to secure their next job, they have to grow strong networking skills, be mobile, and adaptable. These demands take a toll on researchers, especially when considering that they are often employed on short-term, temporary contracts, and work under high pressure in academia to constantly produce high-quality and publication-worthy results. These demands towards academics have a human toll as well and are likely to be a significant determinant of what some have referred to as a mental health crisis in academia (e.g., Bal et al., 2019).

Exacerbating the problem is the fact that universities, unions, and national governments appear either unwilling or unable to take their share of the responsibility in sustaining research careers. Specific researcher populations are more vulnerable than others, especially young, female, and other researchers that are under risk of being marginalised. There is therefore an urgent need, if not a moral imperative, to redress the current state of affairs by enhancing the employability and job security of researchers in and outside of the academic research environment. Making most of the resources invested in educating such specialists is also a fiscal responsibility. It is with good reason that a recent manifesto published by European work and organisational psychologists, a professional group that is ideally positioned to have an opinion on matters pertaining to career development and employee mental health, underscores the importance of recognising the responsibilities we have towards i) placing the well-being of individuals at the heart of management, ii) reducing inequality, iii) breaking the silence in our communities, and iv) democratising the way in which work is organised (Bal et al., 2019).

Therefore, early-career researchers need continuous support to remain employable and should receive training and support in:

- Strategic planning of career steps;
- Reflection on current, desired, and requisite skills in the light of upcoming career steps;
- Personalised training towards these desired and requisite skills;
- Continuous support on transferable skills, with specific attention being paid to stress management;
- Guidance on attaining, maintaining, and sustaining mental health over time.

Given that academia is one of the most globalised sectors of all, with high levels of researcher mobility across countries and continents, and that there are considerable differences in local policies, a transnational approach to addressing these issues is sorely needed.

To meet these challenges, partners in the OSCAR consortium aim to offer a novel set of online learning and mentoring tools to researchers across Europe. OSCAR includes a personalised, state-of-the-art, labour market information based, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) enabled learning recommender complemented by expert career and mental health mentoring. This initiative supports the progress of researchers, doctoral researchers, and research master students towards specific, individual job and skill targets.

Learners will interact with the OSCAR environment through two interrelated components:

1. Learners will interact with an AI powered learning content recommender to construct their own learning trajectories based on relevant labour market information. As an outcome, they will be able to create their individual learning objectives towards jobs and/or specific skills, and receive concrete learning content recommendations from available and relevant Open Educational Repositories (OERs), as delineated in Intellectual Output 2 (IO2).
2. Learners will be able to follow the recommended training and discuss them with experienced career and mental health coaches through online mentoring. This is an important and critical step to reflect on automatic recommendations, to come up with a clear vision and a feasible strategic plan for personal training in the short term, and a career plan to be realised in the longer term (IO3, IO4).

The iterative combination of AI-based recommendations and online human expert based coaching is unique. It has no precedent in the world of (doctoral) education. In this conceptual and technical framework we detail how these two components can seamlessly and synergistically integrate with each other. (IO1)

This OSCAR method will be tested and evaluated through piloting (IO5) with representative European communities of doctoral researchers. During the pilots, special attention will be given to researchers that are under risk of being marginalised, researchers in training, and research master students. The results will be made publicly available as open source and open access products and publications. In addition, an exploitation strategy will be formulated on the basis of the pilot evaluations (IO6).

Mental Well-being Training and Mentoring Framework

State-of-the-art

There are growing concerns in recent years about the mental health of academics and the negative impact of academic workplaces on researchers' mental health (Houston, Meyer, & Paewai, 2006; Winefield & Jarrett, 2001; Eisenberg et al., 2007). According to Badri (2019), academia is a demanding workplace which impacts negatively on researchers' well-being. These demands include but are not limited to ever greater workloads, escalating stress, increased working hours, expanding job scope and changing ways of working, the need to be increasingly sensitive to students' needs and creative to capture their interest, increased focus on performance indicators and rankings between researchers and higher education institutions.

Several studies and reports show that particularly PhD students are at a high risk of experiencing psychological distress, suffering specifically from symptoms associated with depression (Assembly, 2014; Evans et al, 2018; Levecque et al., 2017; Barreira et al., 2018; Peukert et al., 2020, Olsthoorn et al., 2020, van der Weijden et al., 2017), and anxiety (Evans et al, 2018; Barreira et al., 2018; Beadle et al., 2020; Peukert et al., 2020, Olsthoorn et al., 2020). Internationals, (van der Weijden et al., 2017), gender-non-conforming, females (Evans et al., 2018; Olsthoorn et al., 2020), and transgenders (Evans et al., 2018) are at an even higher risk of experiencing mental health issues.

These symptoms seem to increase with time passed in the doctoral program, with more advanced students reporting more symptoms (Barreira et al., 2018, Olsthoorn et al., 2020), less well-being, and less internal motivation (Sverdlik, & Hall, 2019) than beginners. This pattern might reflect the decrease of

structure throughout the program, leading to increased levels of stress (Sverdlik, & Hall, 2019), or the increased pressure to perform or uncertainty about the future (Olsthoorn et al., 2020).

Better mental health in academia is premised on a positive student-supervisor/mentor relationship (Evans et al., 2018; Olsthoorn et al., 2020; Devine, & Hunter, 2017; Hazell et al., 2020), social support, viewing the PhD as a process, engaging in self-care behaviors (Hazell et al., 2020), feeling integrated into the research community (Cornér, Löfström, & Pyhältö, 2017), and a good work-life balance (Evans et al., 2018).

On the other hand, poor researcher mental health has been found to be related to sleep, overall health, academic engagement (Assembly, 2014), work-family conflicts, job demands, job control, team decision-making culture, perception of career outside of academia (Levecque et al., 2017), feelings of low competence (van der Weijden et al., 2017), isolation (Hazell et al., 2020), pressure to perform (Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020), long working hours, working during weekends or vacations (Beadle et al., 2020; Olsthoorn et al., 2020; Peukert et al., 2020; Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020), unstable working conditions, including temporary contracts and financial problems (Olsthoorn et al., 2020), dissatisfaction with supervision (Peukert et al., 2020; van der Weijden et al., 2017; Cornér, Löfström, & Pyhältö, 2017), exposure to harassment, bullying (Peukert et al., 2020; Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020), discrimination and a working culture that normalizes stress and anxiety (Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020). Furthermore, students who fear the consequences of a bad impression, doubt the quality of their work or progress, feel their work is less useful, have less social support, see peers as competitive, and who don't feel comfortable talking about their mental health with their adviser, appear to suffer from poorer mental health (Barreira et al., 2018).

In fact, another aggravating factor is the stigma associated with mental health issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), stigma hinders the prevention and treatment of mental health disorders. Studies show that mental health stigma has a negative effect on help-seeking behaviors (Barney et al., 2006; Vogel, Wade, & Hackler, 2007; Clement et al., 2015; Eisenberg et al., 2009), with some evidence suggesting that stigma can contribute to the development of symptoms of depression (Pyle et al., 2013), anxiety and stress (May et al., 2020).

Additionally, another cause of stress for academics appears to be the peer-to-peer support relationship. A recent report (Loissel et al., 2020) investigated the supportive relationship between some members of the academic community, and PhD students and postdoctoral researchers who struggle with their mental health. Findings showed that most supporters perceive the act of helping others with mental health difficulties as rewarding, but also emotionally draining, time-consuming, and not valued by their institution. As a result, these supporters were also in need of emotional support and practical advice on how to help their colleagues. Most of them were also dealing with their own mental health problems while providing help for more than one person. Specifically, women - in comparison to men - felt their supportive role to be more emotionally draining, more time-consuming, and to have a bigger impact in their personal lives, and work.

Consequently, the current state of academia's mental health might motivate some researchers to abandon their work in science (van der Weijden et al., 2017). In fact, Badri (2019) found that poor work-life balance is connected with poor mental health, lower job satisfaction, and increasing thoughts about leaving or changing institutions, while a good work-life balance is associated with good mental health, increased job satisfaction, and fewer thoughts about leaving or changing institutions. In a different study, the experience of burnout - which was connected with low satisfaction with supervision, low

equality in the research community, and low frequency of supervision - was also associated with considerations about interrupting doctoral studies (Cornér, Löfström, & Pyhältö, 2017).

In light of this research, it becomes essential to develop interventions that aim to promote researchers' well-being and mental health. The literature suggests that interventions should focus on reducing stigma around mental health (Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020; Evans et al., 2018; Beadle et al., 2020), increasing awareness of mental health inequalities (Beadle et al., 2020), promoting a self-care culture and an efficient and mindful work ethic (Evans et al., 2018), expanding the access to mental health support and psychological counselling (Evans et al., 2018; Beadle et al., 2020), including English speaking psychological services in order to create a more inclusive offer (Beadle et al., 2020), facilitating resilience training to help researchers to stay motivated even in the presence of stepbacks (Cerejo, Awati, & Hayward, 2020), as well as mentoring activities to discuss work-life balance and career coaching to develop transferable skills (van der Weijden et al., 2017), and sharing evidence-based information with researchers regarding well-being and mental health (Beadle et al., 2020).

Framework elements

The OSCAR well-being training framework was developed to address the issues identified above, by supporting researchers in dealing with their mental health difficulties through skills training. It was created based on two complementary perspectives of well-being: subjective well-being (Diener, 1984) and psychological well-being (Ryff, 1989).

According to Diener (1984, 2009), subjective well-being consists of the appraisals of one's life, and includes the concepts of life satisfaction (a conscious global judgement about one's life as a whole), and hedonic balance (pleasant minus unpleasant emotional experiences to on-going events). Even though both constructs can be correlated with life events and circumstances, life satisfaction is a global cognitive judgement of one's life, while hedonic level refers to continuous emotional reactions to events. Although subjective well-being is relatively stable across time, it is also malleable and influenced by life circumstances, situations (Fujita & Diener, 2005; Diener et al., 2017; Tay & Kuykendall, 2013), as well as interventions that target the enhancement of well-being (Bolier et al., 2013; Shapiro et al., 2010; Stallman & Kavanagh, 2016).

In a complementary perspective, Ryff (1989; Ryff & Keyes, 1995) explored well-being and gave it the name of psychological well-being. The author built a theoretical model of psychological well-being consisting of 6 dimensions: Self-Acceptance (positive attitude toward the self and past life, accepting good and bad qualities), Positive Relations With Others (creating warm, and trusting relationships with others; showing strong empathy, affection, and intimacy), Autonomy (being self-determining and independent, able to resist social pressures to think and act in certain ways), Environmental Mastery (the ability to manage complex environments to suit personal needs and values), Purpose in Life (having goals in life and a sense of directedness, and actively pursuing them), and Personal Growth (continued growth and development as a person).

Each of these 8 dimensions represent different aspects of well-being, nevertheless they have moderate to large positive intercorrelations (Anglim et al., 2020). In order to create the OSCAR well-being training framework we comprised these dimensions and divided them into five broad domains that represent different and mutually interdependent areas, or components, of psychological functioning and well-being. They are: Emotions (reflects hedonic balance dimension), Behavior & Agency (reflects autonomy dimension), Social Connections (reflects the positive relations with others dimension),

Self-concept (reflects self-acceptance dimension), and Purpose & Meaning (reflects purpose in life dimension).

Some of the dimensions were not directly included in the framework. Life satisfaction and personal growth will probably come as an outcome of the training itself. Environmental Mastery can be trained indirectly through some of these domains (e.g., Behavior & Agency and Social Connections) and, more directly, through OSCAR career management training framework. The domains reflect the dimensions but do not exclusively represent them. Specific skills such as finding a work-life balance, accountability, dealing with perfectionism, were also added.

Each domain is composed of two to four skills that were selected in order to address the common difficulties of researchers.

Figure 1: OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: Purpose and Meaning domain of the OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

The Purpose & Meaning domain – How do I lead a life I value? – consists of the skills Finding Meaning in Life, and Finding Meaning at Work. Learning about what values and directions create meaning and purpose in one’s life is a crucial step for psychological functioning (Hayes, Strosahl, & Wilson, 1999). Since work is such a considerable part of everyday life for researchers and since work conditions and the systemic environment of academia appear to largely explain poor mental health among researchers (see section 1), it might be important to self-reflect about the meaning of work (what in this work creates meaning and purpose in my life?).

Figure 3: Emotion domain of the OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

The Emotion domain – How do I feel? - consists of the following skills: Awareness of Well-being, Recognizing and Understanding Emotions, Emotion Regulation, and Stress Management. To our knowledge there is no definition of Awareness of Well-being, therefore the following definition was created: awareness of the internal and subjective state of well-being. It partly reflects the definition of Grant, Franklin and Langford (2002) of insight, as the clarity and understanding of one’s internal states (thoughts, feelings) and behaviors, however it focuses only on the internal states as a means to evaluate well-being. Recognizing and Understanding Emotions comes as a crucial skill that can potentially mitigate the impact of alexithymia on emotion regulation (Chen et al., 2011; Swart, Kortekaas, & Aleman, 2009). Through the skills of Emotion Regulation and Stress Management the users will be trained on how to deal and respond to the activation of different emotions.

Figure 4: Behavior and Agency domain of the OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

The Behavior & Agency domain – How do I behave/act? – includes the skills Setting Goals, Resilience, Accountability, and Finding a Work-Life Balance. This domain is intimately connected with the Purpose & Meaning Domain. While the latter will help in finding a direction to life, the former consists of behaving in specific (Setting Goals) and continuous (Resilience) ways so that we align with those directions (Hayes, Pistorello, & Levin, 2012). While Accountability involves the cognitive evaluation of one’s behavior, and its consequences, it also comprises a behavioral self-regulation component, because it motivates the person to adjust its actions (Bergsteiner, 2012). Similarly, Finding a Work-Life Balance also reflects behavioral self-regulation.

Figure 5: Social Connection domain of the OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

The Social Connections domain – How do I interact with others? – includes the skills Strengthening Social Relationships, Assertive Communication, and Interpersonal and Social Empathy. Studies show that social connectedness has a positive influence on mental health (Kawachi, & Berkman, 2001; Perkins, Subramanian & Christakis, 2015; Saeri et al., 2017). In order to build positive connections, this framework focuses on the training of the ability to defend personal values (Assertiveness), while accurately feeling and understanding the perspective of the other (Interpersonalization and Social Empathy). This awareness of both perspectives will ask for the negotiation between personal and the other one's needs (Strengthening of Social Relationships).

Figure 5: Self-Concept domain of the OSCAR Mental Well-Being Conceptual Framework

Finally the Self-Concept domain – How do I see and treat myself? – consists of the skills dealing with Perfectionism, Self-Kindness, and Self-Confidence. Studies show that perfectionism is connected with psychopathological symptoms and procrastination (Frost et al., 1990; Hewitt & Flett, 2004; Flett et al., 2007). Therefore, it is crucial to learn how to respond to perfectionism, and to accept mistakes and the non-perfect self (Dealing with Perfectionism). Self-kindness, one component of self-compassion (Neff, 2003a, 2003b), is one helpful way to regulate the harsh and judgmental feelings toward the self (Self-kindness). Lastly, the skill Self-Confidence involves the belief that the self will be able to deal in an effective way with different situations, by focusing on one’s resources or by asking for help when needed.

Discussion

The OSCAR well-being training framework sets out to address academia's mental health difficulties directly through skills training, and also indirectly by bringing awareness to this topic, creating a space of discussion between researchers, which will, hopefully, help in the elimination of the stigma associated with mental health issues in academia.

One possible limitation of this framework is the focus on self-development as a way of promoting mental health, instead of focusing on systemic changes. While some organizations have shown that mental health is linked to systemic issues such as contract types (Olsthoorn et al., 2020) and advocate for changes in that regard, we focus on changes that can be made by the individual. Indeed, this allows us to address in the short-term significant issues for researchers and to have a direct impact on their employability and quality of life, generating a new form of research culture. Some of the skills embedded into OSCAR can help individual researchers to act in ways that can induce over time a systemic change – for example social empathy, accountability, and assertive communication (Segal, 2011; Bergsteiner, 2012; Bergsteiner & Avery, 2003). The academic system may have to adjust to the type of research culture that OSCAR promotes and whereby individual researchers actively take care of their mental health.

OSCAR Career Management and Mentoring Framework

General aim - A framework overview

A career can be defined as the pattern of work-related experiences that spans the course of a person's life (Greenhaus et al., 2000). Labour market and/or employer information form a useful guide to determine the competencies required to be successful in completing certain projects/tasks while being aligned with personal career goals. Competencies can be defined as an individual's set of knowledge and behaviours leading to professional success while skills can be seen as very specific abilities that one needs in order to perform a given job well (Williams, 2005). A person's attitude and motivation typically will determine if and how he/she will start, engage or complete different stages of their career construction (Savickas, 2005). Therefore it is crucial that any career management framework includes a focus on why individuals make certain choices and what makes each step meaningful (Savickas, 2005; Super, 1980).

Early Career Researchers (ECRs) typically are employed on short-term, temporary contracts in a professional context that is often strongly focused on academic output (e.g. publish or perish culture). Given the scarcity of academic positions, young researchers need to develop a wide set of skills that ensure their employability in different sectors. Such durable employment perspectives in- and outside the typical academic sector requires them to develop both "hard", research-specific, skills as well as the more "soft", transferable, skills (e.g. (cross-cultural) communication skills, open science, citizen science, research integrity, networking, teaching, management, leadership, creative and innovative thinking, etc). Training services are therefore needed to help ECRs attaining skills that not only enhance both their current and future performance but also support their professional development, including possible career change(s) (e.g. strategic career planning, reflection, individual training and development plan, continuous transferable skills training, etc.). Our methodology intends to strongly improve learning outcomes through an intricate link between self-managed learning efforts, peer-support, coaching and mentoring services.

The integration of artificial intelligence is a novel approach that allows learners to auto-manage their skills development to a big extent while one-to-one mentoring options remain available when they experience certain obstacles or need guidance and support. Depending on their specific needs and how they wish to use the platform, users can choose from various options. Some users may prefer using the framework to learn and become more aware of relevant skills fitting to their personal and professional development (= broader exploration and awareness). Others may start from more specific and predefined development goals for which they seek training suggestions and coaching (= specific goal development). The full range of content and services available allow users to improve their performance and measure their results over agreed timelines in both an automanaged style or as part of a supervision process. The iterative combination of AI based recommendations and online mentoring is not yet well established within educational programmes and doctoral training in specific. Therefore, we build our framework upon well accepted models of career construction, counselling and guidance.

Modern career theories incorporate a more holistic approach, taking into consideration subjective experiences and personal stories to explain individual career choices (Super, 1980, Savickas, 2005, Hartung & Taber, 2008, Christensen & Johnston, 2003). Career construction theory for instance effectively integrates narrative and career conceptualizations, leading to an increased understanding of what, how and why individuals author their lives and careers (Savickas, 2005). Such holistic clarity helps

individuals in developing a cohesive identity that is adapted to their professional environment and in constructing the next steps in their career story (Savickas, 2005). Within OSCAR this translates to a particular focus on the successful integration of individual self assessment, performance management, skills gap analysis, goal-setting and goal-measurement. To highlight the fluid, connected and varied nature of career options available, we define four knowledge areas through which we invite users to move through, ideally in an iterative procedural flow:

1. **Career Assessment:** the evaluation of one's career that allows for well informed decisions about both the present and future performance, including various possible stages in personal and professional development. This includes both objective aspects (e.g. job position, duty descriptions, etc.) and subjective interpretations thereof (e.g. aspirations, expectations, values, needs, and feelings). Additionally, we include motivation and mind-set as important drivers for career engagement (Caniëls et al., 2018).
2. **Career Management:** the handling of work-related experiences across the professional life span which is focused on job performance outcomes mostly. For our learners, this typically includes the assessment of skills and competencies needed to optimise their current job performance aligned to job descriptions and tasks.
3. **Career Development:** a planned approach to assess both present and (desired) future skills sets that are needed to achieve career goals. This includes techniques such as visualisation exercises, mind mapping, personal reflection, resource planning, goal setting and actions that improve their awareness and skill levels in key areas. Career development is an interactive process, where the individual influences and is influenced by the social, cultural, and physical features of his or her environment (Whiston and Keller, 2004). A similar approach can be used to achieve mental health goals that in turn have an impact on personal motivation and coping strategies (Vuori et al., 2011). Learners will be asked to define their personal development strategy that will be effectively executed and monitored (typically through the creation of an individual development and training plan (IDP and ITP respectively)). Within career development we therefore focus on the assessment of skills and competencies needed for future job performance, integrated in a strategic reflection that paves the way to realise personal career goals.
4. **Career Change:** the process of thinking of, investigating and deciding on career transitions, often triggered by a certain event and the subsequent process of sensemaking. Change can occur in many forms relative to one's career, including both voluntary and involuntary changes with their current employer and/or external opportunities available to them in similar or different sectors. It is common to experience high levels of uncertainty during such a change (Trevor-Roberts, 2006; Trevor-Roberts et al., 2019) and it is crucial that (informed) decisions are based on clearly defined goals that significantly reduce the risks that inherently come with professional change (Deeming & Chelin, 2001; Hodkinson, 2009). For users to become agents of their career development and change, it is important that they experience such a change as intentionally, forethought, self-reactive and self-reflective (Bandura, 2006)

Figure 6 represents the four knowledge areas and how they are integrated in the career management and mentoring framework. Each of the four knowledge areas allows an individual to choose different areas to focus on depending on their present needs and future plans. As such, the knowledge areas

provide different windows for the individual to effectively analyse their current reality and decide on the next steps to take.

OSCAR Career Management & Mentoring Framework

Figure 6. In this figure, we differentiate the Mentoring from the Career Management Framework with the latter nested inside the mentoring framework as a crossroads interconnecting the four knowledge areas.

Strong links between the different knowledge areas together with the motivational components that drive learning processes (Bhakti et al., 2018), allow for a methodological approach to career progression and change. As such, the OSCAR career management and mentoring framework allows learners to improve their attitude, behaviours and skills aligned to the overarching competencies. The training component is driven by an AI algorithm that delivers various online learning contents and formats that are in line with the user's learning preference. The mentoring component is intended to reinforce learning outcomes and to support the attainment of well defined goals.

The OSCAR Career Management & Mentoring framework aims to deliver an effective way of allowing ECRs to effectively assess, manage, plan and evaluate their present and future careers using both technology and human-to-human connection in an integrated single platform. Unique to the OSCAR framework is the creation of an interactive, two components (Artificial Intelligence, AI, and Online Mentoring), online learning environment that allows users to progress their career development. Based on a personalised career assessment and relevant labour market information, the AI component recommends learning content whereas the online mentoring component allows discussion of the recommendations in light of the overall career development goals. Ultimately, OSCAR allows ECRs to (a) reflect on their career management, (b) define individual learning objectives (Individual Development

Plan, IDP), (c) receive concrete learning content recommendations, allowing the construction of an Individual Training Plan (ITP) and (d) discuss career vision and strategic planning with experts and mentors.

Key models for the OSCAR framework

In the following paragraphs we outline the different models that form the backbone of our framework. In order, we introduce (1) the CALP REP Matrix for career assessment, (2) the competency and skills framework for career management, (3) a Wheel of Life inspired diagram for career development, (4) the Widening Horizons Funnel for career change and (5) the GROWTH model as well as the “five steps to success” and BOOST approaches for the mentoring component.

Career Assessment - CALP REP Matrix - A dual lens for career development

Employee Engagement in the general labour market shows to be rather low with for instance only 36% of U.S. employees reporting to feel engaged in their work and workplace (Gallup, 2021). In order to boost employee engagement, it is crucial to take a dual lens approach, including both employee and manager feedback on employee performance, project management and organisation performance (Kwon & Kim, 2020). Since 2016, CALP (Career & Life Planning - <https://calp.ie/>) has been investigating both parties' views on the reasons why exactly difficulties can occur in reaching project goals. From the employee perspective, reasons were varied and included gaps in skills and motivation, a heavy workload but also lack of organisational resources. Managers in turn were often not aware of the many challenges employees were facing as they reported a lack of time to delve into blockages and instead were more focused on the employees' performance instead of their own. It is clear that delays cannot solely be attributed to employee performance or engagement but that both employees and managers are dealing with challenges and that they are often not fully aware of each other's perspective (Baker & Singh, 2015, 2019). Work-related experiences broadly include (a) objective events or situations such as job positions, job duties or activities, and work-related decisions as well as (b) subjective interpretations thereof such as work aspirations, expectations, values, needs, and feelings (Biemann & Braakmann, 2013). Therefore it is crucial to identify the various internal and external barriers for both parties in an integrated system. CALP's solution is the REP matrix, a holistic approach that allows both managers and employees to plan, resource, manage and deliver higher quality projects while constantly viewing the project from a dual lens perspective. The REP matrix model comprises three main pillars that are needed for any task/project completion, namely (a) Resource planning, (b) Employee engagement and (c) Project management. Important to note is that the matrix provides a system approach that also includes employee welfare at its core while inviting the user to examine themselves on various levels of performance.

The REP matrix allows employees and managers (ECRs and supervisors respectively in our case), to better understand the various components that they should be aware of and act on to ensure that both the individual's and the project's goals are realised. The REP matrix allows users to assess their performance with respect to various internal and external resources available to complete the project (incl. motivation, mental health, goal setting and task completion). Besides skills and abilities to complete a task, these resources could delay or block goal achievement when gaps remain unaddressed. User's performance is therefore assessed against five specific components involving (a) character and

competencies for resource planning, (b) capacity and clarity for employee engagement and (c) task completion for project management. In what follows, we further describe the definition and assessment of each of these components.

Resource planning

This pillar focuses on the resources available that are required to deliver the agreed project goals. These resources can be located within the individual, the organisation or both and we make a distinction between the components “character” and “competencies”

- Character. Personal characteristics that impact the individual motivation to complete a project or task, for example: work style, social conditioning, culture, age, gender, moral compass, ethics, education, experience etc. This conglomerate of characteristics strongly impacts decision making processes and therefore the course of action (Gati et al., 2019).

Users will be invited to identify individual patterns of habits that can affect their performance, both in a positive and negative direction based on their own reflection and if they choose, feedback from others who they trust that can engage in this process.

- Competency. The central question here is how confident one feels about their qualification, competencies and skills relative to completing the agreed goal/task? Qualifications, confidence, competence and skills have often been used interchangeably causing confusion and sometimes (mis)perceptions that staff with a certain level of qualifications and experience “should” simply be able to manage their workload. Within the REP matrix we apply the following definitions:
 - Qualifications: certified academic or professional skills training.
 - Competencies: past or present experience proving competency in performing some or all of the required tasks to complete a project. Or in other words, the set of knowledge and behaviours that make the person successful in their job.
 - Skills: various learned abilities that have been acquired and actively used as part of their job. These abilities are needed to perform well in a given job.
 - Confidence: the ability to blend and rely on the qualifications, competencies and skills to achieve the agreed goals.

Users will be invited to map their individual set of qualifications, competencies and skills and how confident they feel in achieving their project goals.

Employee engagement

This pillar focuses on the engagement that is required to deliver the agreed project, taking once again a dual lens approach. Engagement will be assessed through the components “capacity” and “clarity”.

- Capacity. The physical and mental capacity available to complete the assigned tasks. Exhaustion may occur as a result of excessive workload, working culture, physical illness, personal life stressors, etc.

Users will be invited to assess how effective the hours available are being utilised, how both their mental as well as physical capacity may be impacted and how this potentially affects their job and related tasks.

- Clarity. The outcomes of various project goals should be explicitised for both parties involved so that (a) mutual expectations are clear and (b) employees in particular can understand the impact, both positive and negative, that their actions will have on the general project (cf. RACI matrix: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted and Informed; see Smith et al., 2005 for a practical guideline). This will ensure that they feel more connected and help them to plan their efforts more effectively. Once it is clear how their singular actions are integrated in the complex network of goals, it becomes also easier to identify specific skills that will be required.

Users will be invited to assess the overall goal clarity with regard to several types of goals, namely: mental health, physical, team, professional skills, technical and organisational goals.

Project management

This pillar focuses on individuals' past and current work history in terms of effective task completion skills. Users will be asked to reflect on various skills required to successfully plan, manage, communicate and complete their work, allowing the development of consistent highly applicable project management strategies.

- Task completion. In this component, we look at how successful individuals have managed timely task completion in the past and which work style characterises them best. Based on these work styles, patterns and conditioned behaviours, we can then help individuals to improve their performance by reversing old habits, thereby blending past performance with newly acquired habits that will support them in present and future goals.

Users will be invited to assess their habits of completion and both the clarity and integration of project milestones, deadlines, expectations and outcomes.

Table 1 presents a summary of the REP matrix and its components, together with a description of what will be assessed through the OSCAR framework. The REP matrix can be used in various ways, for instance allowing users to either assess their performance in totality as part of their current job or through individual components as part of their individual development plan. Through this self-assessment, they are able to (a) identify where blockages exist in a series of pivotal components and (b) explore solutions to help improve their performance in goal-achievement. Figure 7 in turn provides an example of the self-assessment that users will be completing within OSCAR.

CALP REP Matrix

Pillar	Component	Assessment
Resource Planning	Character	Employees Attitude & Motivation to Work Plus Organisations Resources Available to Complete a Project or Task(s)
	Competency	Technical & Professional Skills Assessment to complete Task(s) or Project
Employee Engagement	Capacity	Physical & Mental Capacity Available to Complete Project or Task(s)
	Clarity	Clear Identification and Alignment of both Employee & Employer goals required to complete Task(s) or Project
Project Management	Completion	“Habit of Completion” to focus on delivery of Task(s) or Project aligned to milestones and Completion Dates

Table 1. CALP REP Matrix

PROJECT GOAL (defined according to SMART principle)						
Resource planning	Character					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stongly agree
	I feel motivated to complete my goal.					
	I have a positive attitude toward the goal					
	Competency					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stongly agree
I possess the technical skills required to complete my goal						
I possess the professional skills required to complete my goal						
I have access to the organisational resources required to complete my goal						
Employee engagement	Capacity					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stongly agree
	I have sufficient mental capacity to complete my goal					
	I have sufficient physical capacity to complete my goal					
	Clarity					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stongly agree
	The mental health goals are clearly defined					
	The physical health goals are clearly defined					
	The collaborative team goals are clearly defined					
	The professional skill goals are clearly defined					
The technical skill goals are clearly defined						
The organisational skill goals are clearly defined						
Project management	Project management					
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stongly agree
	I have the habit of completing my goal timely					
	I am fully aware and integrated into the project milestones, dates and expectations					
I am not fully aware or clear on the project's expectations and outcomes						

Figure 7. A self-assessment tool based on the REP-matrix, allowing users to (a) identify blockages in a series of pivotal components and (b) explore solutions to help improve their goal-achievement performance.

Career Management - Competency and skills framework

Following Donald Supers' Developmental Theory, individuals are expressing their self-concept, or understanding of themselves, when making vocational choices and self-concepts are constantly evolving over time (Super, 1980). Professional roles in which individuals can not only express themselves but also further implement and develop their self-concept will enable them to find career satisfaction (Super, 1980). Within the Career Management knowledge area, users will reflect more widely on the skill set(s) needed in their current job through assessing a selection of competencies and their underlying skills. Figure 8 provides an example of the self-assessment matrix that users will be completing within OSCAR. In particular, our matrix focuses on skills related to (a) Leadership and Management, (b) Research and Research Management, (c) Interpersonal skills and Communication, (d) Personal Care and (e) Professional Skills Management. Users need to rate each skill using a Likert scale measuring to what extent they agree with the following statement "I acquired the following skill and it enables me to perform my job successfully".

OSCAR Career Management Assessment							
Knowledge Area	Competency	Skills	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Career Management	Leadership & Management	Managing Teams					
		Strategic Planning					
		Delegation					
		Commercial Skills					
		Conflict Prevention & Management					
	Research & Research Management	Research Management					
		Project Management					
		Technical (IT) Skills					
		Financial Planning & Management					
		Budgeting & Grant Writing					
		Report Writing					
	Interpersonal & Communication	Open Science					
		Interpersonal & Communication Skills					
		In Class Presentation Skills					
		Social Media Communication & Presentation Skills					
		Digital & Phone Communication Skills					
		Stakeholder Communication Skills					
	Personal Care	Management Communication Skills					
		Intercultural Skills					
		Resilience					
		Work Life Balance					
		Mental Health					
		Physical Health & Self Care					
		Assertiveness					
		Stress Management					
	Professional Skills Management	Self Esteem & Self Confidence					
		Managing Family Relationships					
		Remote Working					
		Collaboration					
		Problem Solving					
Critical & Creative Thinking							
Mobility							
Networking							
Change Management							
Team Work							

Figure 8. An example of the Career Management self-assessment tool allowing users to assess a selection of competencies and underlying skills that allow them to reflect more widely on the skill set(s) needed for their general career progression.

Career development - Wheel of Life inspired spider diagram

Career identity is a structure of meanings in which the individual links his/her own motivation, interests and competencies with acceptable career roles (Meijers, 1998). One's career identity is an important marker for well-being () and constitutes a complex interplay between career and personal variables (e.g. current career stage, career preparation activities, personality factors, physical and mental state, etc.) (Dudovitz et al., 2017, Hartung & Taber, 2008). Based on career development theories such as, Frank Parsons' Trait and Factor Theory (Baker, 2009; Jones, 1994; Parsons, 1909), Holland's Typology (Holland, 1996), Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1989, 2005) and Roe's Personality Theory (Roe, 1956, 1957), users will be encouraged to create their Individual Development Plan (IDP) which incorporates both personal and professional skills that will prepare them for a more balanced and successful career. OSCAR will use a visual representation tool that is based on the Wheel of Life Assessment model (Whitworth et al., 1998), giving the user a visual insight into the gaps between their already acquired set of skills and those that either need to be refined or acquired based on their career aspirations (whether or not they are aligned with their current project).

Figure 9 provides an example of both the career development matrix and the resulting spider diagram that users will be completing in OSCAR. Within this tool, we build further on the set of competencies and skills that were used in the Career Assessment and Management Components but now users will be asked to rate both their present and future (desired) skill levels. Based on state-of-the-art labour market information, OSCAR can then suggest key skill sets in function of specific career aspirations. The results are summarised in a spider diagram that serves as the basis for the individual development plan which focuses on the gaps between current and future (desired) skills levels.

In case the OSCAR framework is primarily used to assess the skills needed for the current job, the above approach also allows users to visualise the desired progression in a similar way, only focusing on the present skills set needed in the current job. This could then result in a career development plan that is focused in particular on the short term development within the current job or project. However, outside of such a modular use, the recommendation is to include middle- and long term goals in the career development so that users can effectively prepare themselves for career progression in the longer term.

Future Skills			
Career Management & Development Matrix			
Skills a user has presently limited awareness or experience in but is interested to improve knowledge & competency in			
Skill	Self Rating Career Management	Career Development Rating	Maximum Level Available
	How you Rate your Present Awareness & Application of these skills	Identify the Rating you would like to Achieve in these Skills	
People Management	1	5	10
Stakeholder Engagement	2	7	10
Leading a Team	1	6	10
Negotiating Skills	1	5	10
Grant Writing	1	7	10
Conflict Management	2	8	10

Figure 9. An example of the Career Development self-assessment tool allowing users a visual insight into the gaps between already acquired skills and those that need to be refined or acquired based on their career aspirations. The resulting spider diagram serves as the basis for the individual development plan.

Career Change - Widening Horizons Funnel

It is rather common for individuals to change their relationship with their career and career goals at different times in their lives for various reasons. The mindset as to when and how someone makes such decisions is important since some changes may be voluntary whereas others are forced. Voluntary career shifts often take a number of months or even years before individuals fully commit to the (desired)

change (Rhodes & Doering, 1983). Involuntary shifts on the other hand can be the result of an abrupt and uncontrollable event that comes as a shock (Ghosh, 2021; Rhodes & Doering, 1983). Career shocks can be defined as disruptive and extraordinary events that are, at least to some degree, caused by factors outside the focal individual's control and that trigger a deliberate thought process concerning one's career” (Akkermans, Seibert, & Mol, 2018). In this regard it comprises two key elements: (1) an event, and (2) a process of (initial) sensemaking. A disruptive and extraordinary event in itself (e.g. unexpected loss of a mentor or valued coworker) is therefore not necessarily a career shock (some may interpret it as a major shock whereas others continue with ‘business as usual’). High levels of uncertainty concerning employment opportunities (Notman and Woolston, 2020) and the strong competition for funding and resources force many ECRs to leave their (anticipated) research career (Marjanovic et al., 2015). When facing such a career change, it is recommended that individuals perform a detailed career assessment and seek advice from qualified professionals in order to make informed decisions that are based on clear goals (Hodkinson, 2009). Doing so, they lower the risk involved with career changes before a decision is made, thereby limiting the impact of emotion (Deeming & Chelin, 2001).

The Career Change Component uses the Widening Horizons Funnel (see figure 10 - Based on material from the Contract Researchers’ Career Development Training Pack © EPSRC October 2002) as a guide to help ECRs visualise short, medium and long-term goals that they can create IDPs for at different stages in their lives. Users will be asked to reflect on the skills required to reach these goals and the change needed to reach the required proficiency levels. Ultimately, this enables users to make well informed training decisions in response to clearly defined personal and professional goals that set the path for professional success and personal enjoyment.

Figure 10. An example of the Widening Horizons Funnel allowing users to visualise short, middle and long term goals for which they can then integrate in their individual development plans.

Mentoring

Mentoring has been shown to make a crucial difference for capacity-building, knowledge transfer and employee retention in many organisations, especially in the educational sector (Baker, 2015; Kalpazidou Schmidt & Faber, 2016). In essence, it involves the creation of a link between two persons that are

passionate about improving professional goals at the end (Abouraiia & Albdour, 2017). Mentoring can be offered at different levels and at all stages in the user’s journey through various formal and informal mentoring types such as traditional, remote, team, peer and group mentoring (Mentor and Mentoring Partnership, 2005). The GROW Model (Goal, Reality, Options, Way Forward) is a widely used and leading coaching tool to help individuals reach their goals (Whitmore, 1992). CALP recently extended it through the inclusion of the “Time for completion” and “How” components, leading up to the GROWTH model (ref) that offers a framework for mentees within OSCAR. For mentors on the other hand, we introduce the “five steps to success” (CALP Coaching Framework - <https://calp.ie/>) and BOOST feedback model (Clayton, 2012), which are further introduced in the following paragraphs. Important to note however is that it is up to the users themselves to decide to what extent they wish to use the mentoring services.

GROWTH model (mentee)

The GROWTH model (Goals, Reality, Options, Way Forward, Time & How) is CALPs extension of the well established GROW Model (Whitmore, 1992). These two additional letters, T (Time for Completion) and H (How), will increase the accountability and task specificity that in turn improve the likelihood of effective outcomes, significantly helping the learners to achieve their goals. Figure 11 provides a visual summary of the GROWTH model.

Figure 11. The GROWTH model as used within OSCAR.

“Five steps to success” and BOOST approach (mentor)

CALP’s “five steps to Success©” model further extends the GROWTH model and provides a mentoring framework that allows mentors to facilitate users’ progress in changing behaviours. These five steps consist of coping, adapting, improving, maintaining and enjoying (www.calp.ie). This approach provides a proven blend of techniques that guides users through a process allowing them (a) to deal effectively with

the challenges ahead (coping), (b) to explore various adaptive mindsets to their situation (adapting), (c) to identify areas for improvement within their control (improving), (d) to develop new habits, systems and strategies to maintain momentum (maintaining) and (e) to visualise enjoyment and success within both their personal and professional lives (enjoying). The sequential flow provides an effective tool to help individuals to manage change while integrating multiple levels of cognitive, visual, behavioural and emotional skills related to goal setting and a systemic approach to sustainable change.

In providing feedback to Mentees, Mentors are strongly advised to use the BOOST approach (Clayton, 2012). It is an informal feedback model that is used to give constructive and continuous feedback about both positive behaviour as well as shortcomings that should be rectified. As such, the BOOST model involves a sequence of steps to effectively communicate and support the user in giving feedback that is Balanced, Observed, Objective, Specific and Timely.

Integration and presentation of the OSCAR structure

Users are recommended to follow an iterative procedural flow, allowing them to use all modules in a sequential order. Starting with the REP matrix, users will (a) identify patterns of habits affecting their performance, (b) mapping their individual set of qualifications, competencies and skills, (c) expressing their level of confidence in goal achievement, (d) assessing their mental and physical capacity as well the overall goal clarity and (e) reflecting on their habits of completion. In a second step, users reflect more in depth on the set of skills and competencies needed in their current job (career management) and/or (desired) future job (career development). Based on the resulting spider diagrams, users can easily identify gaps between their already acquired set of skills and those that either need to be refined or acquired based on their career aspirations (whether or not they are aligned with their current project). Finally, users are invited to reflect about their professional development and possible career changes needed to reach the required proficiency levels. When users wish or need, they can request mentoring and coaching through their trajectory. Figure 12 gives a visual summary of the different modules that can be either taken as a full trajectory (recommended) or as independent development modules.

Ultimately, OSCAR allows users to proactively tackle their individual career development, thereby making well informed training decisions in response to clearly defined personal and professional goals that set the path for professional success and personal enjoyment.

Visual Integration of OSCAR Career Framework

Figure 12. A visual summary of the different modules that are available to the user. The recommendation is to go through all of them sequentially, using mentoring or coaching when wished for and then iterate the process.

Framework for AI-based Training and Mentoring Recommendations

In order to offer access to the above-mentioned concepts of mental well-being and career management, OSCAR's technical framework is developed as a user-centric platform with AI-based learning content recommendations. The technical framework includes a personalised learning space, where early-career researchers can access all recommended learning materials. It also brings together mentors and mentees, for cases that require a human-expert assessment of learners' well-being, or coaching needs.

State of the Art

Using AI-based recommendations in a traditional learning environment won't be as effective for users as a newly designed, user-centred application with integrated Machine Learning algorithms. Although most user experience designers are behind the Machine Learning technology developments, Machine Learning is still considered to be very important in improving the user experience (Dove 2017; Yang 2017). Using Machine Learning properly in the final product creates a unique experience for each individual user, thus this level of personalization can significantly increase ease of use, motivation and a feeling-like-home experience in users.

Currently, it is widely believed that integrating Machine Learning (which is the core element of Artificial Intelligence) into the user experience has numerous problems that need to be tackled. These problems consist of misconceptions regarding the power of intelligent systems, lack of technical tools available, and integration strategy (Dove 2017; Yang 2017; Browne 2019).

Furthermore, as the quantity of online educational content is increasing on the internet continuously, finding appropriate content is time consuming. The lack of learning-specialised and personal search engines and recommenders is a big obstacle in the path of enthusiastic learners. In this situation, providing an AI-based training system can play an important role in facilitating the process of online learning. To fill the existing hole in the area of online learning, we have been building an intelligent system that can help learners not only to find the content they need, but also create a personalised learning path to fulfil their personal learning requirements (Tavakoli et al, 2020). This AI-based training system consists of two main parts: user data and educational content.

As a first step, we are gathering the basic information of users like their geographical location, gender, age, professional experience, and previous education. We also enhance the individual profile of each learner by questions directly referring to the user's learning preferences or even their current wellbeing. The answers combined with the basic user profile data provide very useful information for our machine learning engine to detect users' actual learning needs and preferences. As the AI-core knows its learners, eventually by getting feedback from the users, it can provide even more relevant content and learning paths to the learners with similar preferences.

The second pillar of our AI-based training system is the pool of high quality open educational content. This content is spread across the internet, therefore, the very first step is to gather as much data on learning content as possible. Fortunately, there are a handful of educational repositories, like youtube, which can make a great starting point for this work. Subsequently we need to assess the quality of the gathered data. This will be done by using metadata and technical measurements to assess the quality of the gathered learning content automatically (Elias et al, 2020). After quality filtering, we use machine learning models to extract the topics and skills, which are covered by educational resources. Based on this information, we categorise the gathered data and make them ready for learning recommendations.

Using the metadata of educational content, the system will attempt to create a correlation between educational resources and user profiles. Users' feedback on each educational resource therefore plays an important role in (re)shaping this connection.

Technical Implementation

OSCAR's technical framework is designed to combine the advantages of intelligent decision support algorithms with the requirements of a healthy researcher career development. Components of the framework are shown in Figure 13. Each of those components corresponds to a requirement that has been determined by the wellbeing and career development conceptual frameworks.

The users of the framework include mainly the learners and the mentors. They both interact with the technical system through an interface, which provides all the necessary functions to receive the recommended materials, communicate with other users, express the user's mood and provide input and feedback about the learning material itself. The system also provides users with an individual dashboard to track their learning progress. The interface is directly connected to the decision-making algorithm, which takes the form of a graph-based recommender system. The recommendations are generated based on two main pillars: 1) the user profile, which provides the recommender with information about the user's learning history, current status and future goals, and 2) the learning-material knowledge-base, which semantically relates the non-technical learning materials, i.e. on career management and mental well-being, to the required skills for a healthy career-development process. The framework additionally features a user mood-detector, which is designed to acquire the user's self-assessment on their current wellbeing, as well as to measure psychological indicators that are highlighted in the conceptual framework. Those are then stored in the user profile and used to influence the recommendations. Those are then stored in the user profile and used to influence the recommendations.

Figure 13. OSCAR project's technical framework

Learning materials are evaluated along several dimensions, including automatic quality assessment (Tavakoli et al., 2020), as well as crowdsourcing based feedback. The crowdsourcing function aims at collecting input from users about the recommended learning materials, in terms of their content and technical quality, appropriateness, etc. In the following subsections, the components of our technical environment are presented and discussed in more detail.

Graph based recommender system

The learning content recommender component in OSCAR's technical framework meant to provide the user with suitable suggestions based on their individual profile and personal goals. Among multiple recommendation algorithms, we adopt a knowledge-graph based approach, due to its capability of representing the relations not only between the user and the recommended materials, but also the relations amongst users, and the relations amongst the materials. To construct the knowledge graph, we have developed the EduCOR ontology (Ilkou et al, 2021) that represents the concepts required for a learning recommendation, linking this recommendation to the users profiles and the skills needed for a healthy career development. The resulting knowledge graph is a network of inter-connected users and materials, allowing the generation of semantic recommendations to a certain user, based on the overall knowledge about the user themselves. Such knowledge has been embedded in the graph's nodes and relations, and therefore can be retrieved from them to build the recommendation.

As a result of the semantic relations in the graph, as well as the embedded knowledge about the user and the materials, the recommendation itself can have multiple types, corresponding to e.g. the mental well-being of the user or their available time. The developed recommender in this framework is designed to recommend learning topics, learning materials, full learning paths that are composed of a sequence of topics, tests or quizzes, and learning actions, such as getting some rest before starting the learning or talking to a mentor about a certain issue.

To be able to generate those types of recommendations, an accurate representation of the user is essential. Learning materials and actions also need to be well modelled in the system. Therefore, user and learning-material modelling form two of the main components in OSCAR's framework.

User modelling

The more comprehensive user information is, the more accurate the recommendations can be. In the context of a researcher's career development, a multitude of parameters, including the user's learning performance, mental well-being, and learning preferences need to be taken into consideration when suggesting an action to the user. The conceptual framework, including the mental well-being and career coaching pillars, have honed onto a set of parameters that need to be considered by the technical implementation of the recommender system. Those parameters are stored in the user profile and continuously updated with changes in the user's status. The user profile is designed in the technical framework to provide the recommender with an accurate model of the user at any point in time. It includes a history of the user's actions, the user's current learning preferences, future learning goals, the user's academic performance, and the psychological state of mind of the user. Academic parameters are captured through a set of measurable indicators, such as test grades. Psychological parameters are represented by high-level psychological constructs, such as tiredness, or focus, and tangible indicators that are used to detect those constructs. An example of a psychological indicator can be the time needed

to answer a question, for example, which, in a certain context, may reflect tiredness. The definition of those indicators and constructs is derived from the elements of OSCAR's framework, and determined by the mental well-being and career coaching experts of the OSCAR project.

Learning material representation

Recommending learning content for career- and mental-health development requires the system to model the links between learning materials and the skills needed for developing the user's career and mental wellbeing. To address this challenge, this technical framework adopts a semantic representation of learning materials themselves through an ontology structure. In the developed ontology (Ilkou et al., 2021), skills, learning resources, topics, and recommendations are represented as concepts. They are then connected through the ontology's relations, enabling the recommender systems to find the semantic link between each learning material and the targeted skill. The ontology used for modelling learning materials includes the connections to the user's profile, the actual recommendation that the user is receiving, and the career-oriented skills that the user is aiming for. Additionally, concepts in the ontology are designed to cover the possible recommendations that the user can get. Tests and learning paths are examples of recommendations that are represented by independent concepts in the ontology, alongside the skills, knowledge topics and learning resources. It is important to mention that the ontology developed in this context, forms a foundation stone in the construction of the full knowledge graph, which is, in turn, used by the recommender system to generate the semantic recommendations.

Crowdsourcing

In this section, we explain our crowdsourcing platform, in which users contribute to the collection and the curation of different educational components (i.e. high level (learning) goals, skills, topics, learning resources, tests) in our system. Here, we clear the steps to add a new component to our system:

- **Skill.** To offer learning pathways to users, we needed to decompose skills into meaningful knowledge topics. Users can define a skill by three fields of 1) skill title, 2) skill description, and 3) list of related topics. To facilitate this process and to show (and recommend) the most related learning topics, we automatically collect large amount of educational materials on a particular new skill and extract existing topics from those collected learning materials (Molavi et al., 2020).
- **Learning Materials.** As one of the most important steps in creating a learning path, high-quality educational materials are needed to be added into our system continuously. To achieve this, we developed a feature, which helps human contributors to add educational materials to the system by showing them a list of related educational resources for each learning topic. These educational materials are crawled automatically from open/free websites (e.g. Youtube) and need to pass our quality control component. Each collected learning material should contain the following features:
 - Title
 - Description
 - Content-format (e.g. videos, web pages, slides)
 - Length (the time required (in second) to learn the resource)
 - Target learning topics (the subjects that are covered by the resource - extracted by our topic models)

- **Assessments.** To offer assessment services to learners in our crowdsourcing platform, contributors can also add tests for each topic. These tests are used for creating assessments at both skill and topic levels in order to aid learners to monitor their progress towards their learning objectives.

Furthermore, when adding or editing a particular component, the following rules are applied:

- All types of users (learner or expert) can define a new component
- To edit (as well as adding, editing, or deleting a subcomponent), users submit their suggestions. All suggestions should be reviewed by the crowd except if they have been submitted by experts.
- Users can vote (upvote or downvote) a suggestion. The effect of a user's vote is decided based on their vote-points in that specific skill or topic. The vote-power in high-level goals is always 1.
- A suggestion is accepted if it achieves the minimum number of vote-points (60 vote-points) and 60% percent of them are upvotes. Otherwise, the suggestion is rejected. It should be mentioned that suggestions are rejected if they do not receive the minimum number of votes after a week.

To motivate users to contribute to our platform, we will implement a leaderboard feature. According to this feature each user will gather a vote-point for each individual skill and topic under the following situations:

- User creates a skill or topic
- User's suggestions in a skill or topic is accepted by another user
- Learners add a skill or topic (which is created by the user) to their learning dashboard

Vote-point in each skill and topic increases the weight of the user's opinion in the respective skill or topic. Each user has 1 vote-point by default for all skills and topics.

Learning Dashboard

We build a learning dashboard, in which users can monitor and adjust their learning objectives. This is done through the following steps:

1. As the first step, users build up their profile to provide contextual information for the system. This information includes name, birthdate, geographical location, educational level.
2. After finishing the first step of the registration, users can search through the high-level learning goals and select those they want to meet. Based on the selected learning goals, the list of related skills are displayed to the users. For example, if a user sets "Planning" as a high-level learning goal, he/she receives a list of related skills such as "Time management" and "Task prioritisation". Afterwards, users can select skills from the list they want to target. Additionally, users can search and add skills and learning topics directly to their learning targets.
3. To offer personalised recommendations, the system asks some questions to capture the learning preferences of the new user. These questions capture user preferences regarding learning content-format, length, level of details, classroom-based content, etc. The answers to these questions are stored as preference vectors in the user profile.
4. The system will create a customised learning pathway for the new users based on the data provided in the previous steps. Users can view their learning goals, and learning pathways towards those goals. The recommended path includes all knowledge topics that should be covered to achieve learning goals. Personalised educational resources recommendations are associated with each topic in the individual learning pathway. The system offers the closest educational materials to each user, based on their contextual information (e.g. country and

language), learning goals, and the preference vectors that have been created in the previous steps. It should be mentioned that the system accounts user behaviour (e.g. feedback provided for the recommended learning materials, or user performance in assessments), which is saved in *User Logs* to update preference vectors. This method is essential to capture changes in user preferences.

5. Finally, to help users to monitor their progress towards their learning goals, we provide skill-level and topic-level assessments using the collected and verified questions in our crowdsourcing platform. Moreover, our system offers various statistics and charts, based on the results of assessments to provide a clear insight for both learners and their mentors.

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